

Our project is supported by the Arctic Connections Fund

Inspiring Visitor Engagement with Rural Cultural Heritage Tourism
Creating a local heritage audio trail

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UNIVERSITY OF LAPLAND

Dr Katie Murray, UHI NWH,
Kendra Turnbull UHI, NWH,
& Dr Monika Luthje,
University of Lapland

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Inspiring Visitor Engagement with Rural Cultural Heritage Tourism – Creating an audio trail

For over six months in 2023 and 2024 researchers at the University of the Highlands and Islands and the University of Lapland each worked with a local community to create an audio trail showcasing their local heritage.

We wanted to investigate how to support small, sparsely populated and under-visited destinations to safeguard and celebrate their heritage and promote their tourism offering in a way that is sustainable, regenerative and accommodates the needs of the local community.

In Scotland the participating community was Ardgour, on the west coast of the Scottish Highlands and near the popular tourist attractions of the Glenfinnan Viaduct, the iconic landscapes of Glencoe, and the Ardnamurchan Peninsula, the most western point of the British mainland.

In Finland we worked with a village association of residents of nine villages in the Upper Kemijoki Region, north of the Arctic circle and adjacent to Rovaniemi, the administrative capital of Lapland and home to a tourism industry centred around Santa Claus, northern lights and husky sledding.

These areas were chosen as they are often overshadowed by more famous tourist destinations nearby, and struggle to position themselves within the tourism market. This project sought to demonstrate that these communities have a rich cultural and natural heritage, and how to celebrate and preserve this.

Here we share what we did and the lessons we learned so that other communities, which might want to market themselves and preserve their culture in the same way, can follow these examples.

Why create a digital platform for your heritage?

1

You can promote and share authentic local culture, with both locals and potential visitors.

2

Knowledge that might have been lost will be passed on and preserved.

3

Sharing stories can inspire a sense of pride in locals and deepen the meaning the place has to them.

4

The act of gathering stories can help forge intergenerational connections, imbuing a sense of place and belonging and strengthening social cohesion.

5

The act of sharing the stories can help connect visitors to the place and potentially attract new ones, even some who are unable to visit the place physically.

6

You can gear the platform towards the needs of your community, telling the stories you want to tell and directing visitors to the sites you want them to visit.

7

Sometimes there is little up-to-date or accurate information available in guidebooks or online - this helps plug the gap and attract visitors.

Examples of trails, audio recordings and digital heritage storage curated by communities.

Stories of Korkalovaara (Tarinoita Korkalovaarasta) was a project run by the University of Lapland to collect local stories of the suburban area of Korkalovaara in Rovaniemi. The project created its own digital platform for the stories, which are located on a map in a written format. They make visible suburban culture in Lapland and are accompanied by photos and drawings. The platform and the stories are in Finnish. The decade from which the stories date is indicated at the end of each story and stories can be searched by decade. Anyone can send a story through a form available on the platform.

What we learned?

- Short stories also work also in a written format. The stories from Korkalovaara are written in a vernacular language, which gives them a local flavour.
- Simple drawings by a graphic designer can catch the essence of a place.
- Knowing when the events of the story have taken place is important for the reader.

Wick Voices began collecting recordings in 2016 and now has a huge archive. All the recordings are collected by volunteers and they use non-specialist equipment such as mobile phones, laptops, and free editing software. They meet people in their homes or wherever they feel most comfortable and relaxed. Both young and old contribute, and they invite stories about everyday life both as well as histories and legends. In this way they have created a record of life in Wick, incorporating lots of different voices. As well as publishing these on a website they have developed a way for the recordings to be accessed through an old rotary phone, opening up access for those who are not digitally literate.

What we learned?

- The thought of being recorded can be intimidating - Wick Voices makes it as relaxed as possible.
- Audio does not need to be professionally recorded and produced to be worthwhile.
- Personal reminiscences can make for powerful and compelling stories.

Discover Cullen has created an interactive app which showcases trails, and their associated heritage, around Cullen. It promotes local businesses and hosts quizzes and challenges to undertake while you are on the walks.

Each trail is accurately marked on a Google map background and contains clear information about the length, gradient, underfoot conditions and accessibility levels. There are also written instructions directing you around the trail. On each trail there are a series of physically installed QR codes, locations of which are plotted on the map. There are a series of quizzes and challenges to encourage further interaction on the walks, such as a Doric language quiz or flora and fauna spotting.

What we learned?

- The app is simple and clear to use and is a great way to store lots on information in one place.
- A purpose-built app means the information provided is accurate and presented in a way which best serves the needs of the community.
- Online trails work well when supported by physical markers.
- It is an expensive option which requires upkeep.

What we did

Scotland

- Produced a map with a proposed trail and suggested stories and circulated this beforehand.
- Hosted an event in a community space. This was promoted locally beforehand by a local facilitator. At the event we introduced what we wanted to do and the reasons why and presented examples of other digital platforms that had inspired us, before having a discussion what local heritage people thought was important and what stories they would like to see featured in the trail. We then asked for volunteers to take ownership of one of the stories, carrying out those parts they felt most comfortable with such as research, writing and recording.
- Over the next three months the UHI researchers then worked with them on whichever aspects of the stories they wanted assistance with. We proofed and suggested edits to text and facilitated recording using professional equipment when desired. We used story contributors' local knowledge by asking them to supply or suggest appropriate images and where the stories should be plotted on the map.
- UHI researchers edited the audio tracks when needed and managed uploading all the content to the Geotourist platform.
- When the trail was near completion, we held a second workshop where we invited all the contributors as well as the wider community, to come and see the trail, listen to the tracks, and provide feedback on the story titles and text blurbs. We made final edits based on this.
- Following leadership from the community we created posters, a leaflet, outdoor signs and social media posts to promote the trail.

Finland

- Planned a workshop together with the village association board. The workshop was promoted on social media, in the local newspaper and on University of Lapland's website. It was open to all local residents to participate.
- Facilitated the workshop in the village school outside school hours. In the workshop, the project and the Geotourist platform were introduced together with the trail planned in Ardgour. The workshop participants planned together a trail that would cover all the nine villages. One participant drew the trail on paper while others were suggesting and telling stories. Three stories were chosen as pilots and responsibilities were shared concerning who would do what and by when.
- Gave instructions concerning the story scripts, recordings and images and provided assistance where required.
- Collected all the materials created by the local residents, uploaded them in the Geotourist platform and tested the trail on site.
- Arranged a second workshop to introduce the trail to the local residents and to encourage them to create more stories for it. The workshop was outdoors on one of the pilot stops of the trail and arranged in collaboration with the village association. It was promoted in Facebook and the local newspaper and generated new story and workshop plans.
- Promoted the trail on social media and via a media release. The local destination management organisation and business development agency were also informed about the trail.

How to create an audio trail- what we learned

We found it vital to have a strong local facilitator who understands the project and is embedded in the community. It is easier to work with people you are familiar with compared to working with strangers.

Be a facilitator and coordinator, letting the community work in its own way (in the Upper Kemijoki River area the village association chair took the lead in the workshops).

Make your events open to everyone- but target your 'knowledge carriers' - the people you know will be both enthusiastic and have stories that can help to start a conversation.

Try to involve different demographics or generations - for example in Scotland the local school provided a story and audio.

Having a prompt, such as an outline of a proposed trail, existing work to build on or an annotated map with suggested stories helps people understand the project and trigger conversation more easily than trying to start from scratch.

Consider where trail stops will be being mindful of safety and comfort for the listener, underfoot conditions or vegetation areas that shouldn't be trampled on and privacy for peoples land or houses.

Get participants enthused about the project before inviting them to contribute. Show them inspirational case studies and other examples.

Set clear parameters based on best practice from the very beginning - for example, the length of the recording. Then nobody feels cheated and like they have wasted their time if they produce a 10 minute recording when you wanted a maximum of three.

Allow participants to engage in the parts of the story creation they are most interested in and comfortable with. Some might be happy to write a story but not to record it - allow this and help to facilitate those parts that are missing.

Supply advice on getting a good recording at home.

Supply advice on free editing platforms and platforms for hosting the trail, to empower communities to continue the work after the main project is over.

Make sure someone listens to and reads the trail in its entirety to spot errors, inconsistencies, and little ways it could be improved. Use a fresh pair of eyes, ideally someone with local knowledge - in Scotland we invited participants to do this during the second workshop- and the feedback was invaluable, in Finland the village association chair took responsibility.

Audio recording guidance

Location

- Find a quiet place to record - under the duvet is ideal, but otherwise a room with soft furnishings to absorb background noise. Be aware of and try to reduce background noise such as ticking clocks, electronic hum from fridges and TVs, traffic and pets.

Equipment

- If you have a digital recorder and microphone that is ideal, but otherwise any recording/playback device such as a smartphone, iPad, tablet or laptop will work.
- Most models and devices come with an app or program to record audio already pre-installed (for example 'Voice Memos' on Apple devices, 'Recorder' on Android, 'Voice Recorder' on Windows).
- Most audio formats are fine and can be easily converted to mp3.

Set Up

- Place your device in front of you on a flat surface- this reduces shake and standardises the distance between your mouth and the microphone.
- Use a tablemat or mouse mat to absorb vibrations.

Recording

- Have the story on a screen or printed out in a font that is easy to read. Break the text down into short and readable sections and ensure there is no need to turn a page mid-sentence or mid paragraph.
- Pause between reading each section. This way, if you make a mistake, or there is sudden background noise, then you just need to rerecord this section.
- You can use the pause button if you want a break or to gather your thoughts.
- If you make a mistake or stumble over your words, then wait five seconds and repeat that section or sentence, as this can be edited later. Consider recording each section a couple of times, with pauses in-between.
- Read the story aloud but try to make it sound 'told' rather than 'read' (think radio presenter).

Geotourist guidance

We used the Geotourist platform to host our audio trails but there are other platforms available. Geotourist has a section on tour creation FAQs to help guide you but here are few things to think about.

Choose a photo that will work well on a mobile phone screen.

In the 'add' section you can add extra elements, links or quizzes.

When selecting the location think about where the listeners can safely stand and utilise the radius selector to pinpoint the location - especially if you have a few stories close together.

If your path is not visible on the map there is a satellite option to help you locate the correct spot.

For the description you want to tempt your audience into listening to the audio, so don't just transcribe it. It is also a good place to include directional information or to link to the next story.

For your audio aim for around a length of two minutes (approx. 230-300 words).

Keep text short as users are likely to be on mobile phones with small screens.

To ensure all recordings are the same volume see if your software can match the sound level. The setting EBU R128 is the standard level to look for.

Once finished, take the tour yourself to check for repetition, that audios are at similar volumes and that you are happy with the flow.

The tours

'A walk in Ardgour' on the Geotourist platform, and associated leaflet, QR code signs and poster.

Audioreittietappi

Lataa Geotourist-sovellus ja kuuntele tämän paikan tarina

Yläkemijoki tour on the Geotourist platform and the QR code signs on the tour.

What else could you do with the stories collected?

Once you have collected the stories there may be an interest within the community to develop the idea further. Our communities decided they wanted some physical representation of the trail in the form of QR codes, leaflets and posters.

Other ideas could include:

Physical representation- notice boards

Storytelling evenings

Theatrical play

Creating an event around the trail

Quizzes or hunts

Taking it further to create a community app

There may be interest to take the idea even further and develop a full community tourism app, such as the example below from Discover Cullen. This could include the stories, along with other useful information.

App guidance

Developing an app is expensive. It will require a professional developer. At the time of writing (February 2024) you can expect to pay £25,000+ and so this will almost certainly require fundraising.

Think carefully about whether it is worth creating an app. One advantage is that it gathers all the essential information into one place and is easy to signpost visitors to, but it will involve a lot of money and effort which might be better directed elsewhere, such as promoting your community across different websites and social media channels. Think about factors such as the size of your community and the demographics of your visitors - are they likely to use an app?

Information which could be featured in the app:

- Local tourism businesses such as hospitality and experience providers.
- Local facilities such as toilets and Wi-Fi.
- How to get here? Information or links to the website of local transport providers.
- Inspirational images and video of the local area.
- Information about local historic and natural sites and walks, linked to reputable outside agencies such as Historic Environment Scotland and NatureScot.

This type of information can go out of date quickly. Businesses can shut down or change their opening hours, bus and ferry timetables can change. We recommend 'future proofing' your content as much as possible by linking to website or social media pages that are likely to be kept up to date rather than supply information directly. Keep information as timeless as possible for minimum maintenance and upkeep, but know who is able and responsible for going 'behind the scenes' and changing any information needed in the app when necessary.

Consider making the app interactive using

- Gamification.
- Augmented or virtual reality elements.
- GPS triggered notifications which:
 - Give discounts or offers to entice users into local businesses.Suggest things to look at or do.

Potential sources of funding in Scotland:

- National Lottery 'Awards for All' have supported digital projects in the past.
- National Lottery Heritage fund.
- Historic Environment Scotland 'Historic Environment Grants' can support community projects focused on digital preservation of heritage.
- Paths for All.
- Local industries such as energy companies or fish farms might be willing to contribute.
- Local businesses who will be featured or benefit from increased visitation.

Potential sources of funding in Finland:

- Leader funding can be applied for local-level community development projects in rural areas.
- The Finnish Cultural Foundation's Regional Funds give grants to support cultural and heritage work. For example, the Stories from Korkalovaara project received funding from the Lapland Regional Fund.
- There may also be other national, regional or local foundations or funds that grant funding for cultural and heritage projects in Finland. For example, the town of Rovaniemi has a foundation that gives grants to local villages to increase their attractiveness and promote their cultural and recreational activities and livelihoods.
- The Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture is also a potential funding source. It gives grants, among others, to cultural and heritage tourism development projects.

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Ardgour Audio Trail ideas...

Following on from the 'Welcome to Ardgour' project IHI have funding from the Scottish Government's Arctic Connections Fund to develop an audio trail. This is aimed at connecting people to their local heritage, protecting that heritage and utilising it as a tool for tourism. We will show you ways in which other communities have recorded their heritage and work with you to create a trail that reflects what you want to showcase or learn about. This page presents a route and ideas to get us started.

If you were walking around Ardgour what would you like to learn about?

Join us in Ardgour Hall on Wed 25th Oct, 6.30pm start

